

METHODS OF DEVELOPING MANAGEMENT CULTURE OF LEADERS IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article discusses the role of young leaders in New Uzbekistan, the requirements for them, and the work being done to develop the potential of young leaders in New Uzbekistan. There is talk about what kind of culture the leaders will have in new Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *young leaders, New Uzbekistan, Third Renaissance, IT technologies, science, innovations, leadership culture.*

Introduction. The concepts of "New Uzbekistan" and "Third Renaissance" were widely and actively used in the recent interview of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the editor-in-chief of the newspaper "Yangi Uzbekiston". The most important thing is that in most places, it is possible to observe that both concepts come side by side, harmoniously. When it comes to this, first of all, it should be noted that there are few state and public figures who enrich world political terminology with new concepts in the international experience. From this point of view, the fact that the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev introduced the concept of "New Uzbekistan" into the dictionary of world politics is of incomparable scientific importance. New Uzbekistan is a phrase put forward by the President and today it has a deep place in the hearts of all our people. It's a great idea that's becoming a nationwide movement. At the heart of this idea: on the one hand, the noble goals of today's and tomorrow's generations to lay the foundations of the "Third Renaissance"; on the other hand, the aspirations and dreams of our great ancestors, great grandfathers who founded the First and Second Renaissance periods in our national history; on the third hand, creativity and the call to always study and research are embodied. As noted by the President, who is considered to be an architect and initiator of New Uzbekistan, "Establishment of New Uzbekistan is not just a desire, a subjective phenomenon, but a political, legal, social - it is an objective necessity that is demanded by the economic, spiritual and educational situation, corresponds to the age-old aspirations of our people, and fully meets its national interests. First of all, in the words of our President, the word "new" has a special meaning for us. In this sense, it is not without reason that in the Strategy of Actions adopted five years ago, we set ourselves the great tasks of building a New Uzbekistan and creating the foundation of the Third Renaissance as a strategic goal. In the interview of the President, we talked about the high results achieved in various spheres of our life and the responsible tasks ahead of us in this regard.

Research Methodology. On the other hand, under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the main goal was to create the foundations of a new renaissance in Uzbekistan, that is, the Third Renaissance. As the head of our state noted, "We put the issue of the Third Renaissance in front of us as a strategic task and raise it to the level of a national idea" that means re-emergence, rebirth, resurrection, revival. The term "Renaissance" was first used in the 16th century by the architect, painter and art historian George Vasari (1511-1574). Used to describe the historical period conditioned by the initial stage of the development of bourgeois relations in Western Europe. The current meaning of this revolution was introduced by Farang historian Jules

Michle (1798-1874) in the 19th century. The concept of "Muslim Renaissance" was introduced to the science of history by the famous Austrian orientalist Adam Metz (1876-1946) at the beginning of the 20th century, more precisely, in 1909. The scientist used the term "East" in a historical sense, referring to the lands from the Mediterranean Sea to the European continent, and in these regions, culture rose to heights in the 9th-12th centuries. These countries are the cradle of ancient civilization. During the former Soviet era, only the Western Renaissance was discussed in history and educational literature. Not much was said about the Renaissance process in the East. Because the idea of Eurocentrism prevailed in the science of history, the doctrine of "the West is advanced, the East is backward" prevailed. However, our great ancestors founded not one, but two Enlightenment Renaissances in history. The first Eastern Renaissance - the "Enlightenment Renaissance" that took place in our region in the 9th-12th centuries.

Of course, the role of young leaders is incomparable in the fact that our country is entering the Third Renaissance and the countries of the world are increasingly interested in studying our New Uzbekistan. That is why, in the period of rapid reforms that are continuing in our country today, great attention is paid to young people with progressive thinking and potential, and they are attracted to political fronts and strategically important areas. The requirements of the modern society are piecemeal. It encourages citizens to care for the development of the country and the nation, to look at life deeply and carefully. [2:50]. In the last five years, every citizen of our country has seen a state with incomparable change, renewal and fundamental reforms, which he deeply feels in his daily life. Political-legal and socio-economic modernization of society, spiritual restoration and improvement, revision of existing laws, state administration, economic system, creation of effective and efficient mechanisms in this regard, implementation of democratic principles and norms. [3:44] In order to support the policy of our Honorable President towards the establishment of New Uzbekistan, we will have to take a step forward with our hands folded. In the organization of experimental work, first of all, after assessing students' psychological readiness for the lesson, their interests, scientific and creative worldviews, i.e., their creative abilities, using demonstration organizers, demonstration models and handouts, clusters and questions are used in the lesson. The need to develop the management culture based on a creative approach to the success of the leader, the culture of management employees depends on many factors, the level of general culture, business qualities, deep and comprehensive knowledge of management science and the ability to apply it in the course of their activities. They will have knowledge about becoming, understanding the purpose of the State policy on youth, social support for young people, creating the necessary conditions for them, creating a healthy moral environment in the community. The concept of management culture based on a creative approach is a generalizing indicator of the level of development and has several meanings. For example, it is possible to talk about the culture of society, the culture of some individuals, and finally, the culture of some type of human activity [3]. Human activity is divided into types that create material and spiritual wealth. Therefore, material and spiritual culture are distinguished. Material culture is an indicator of the degree of human subjugation of nature. It includes means of production and objects of labor. Spiritual culture can include science, the level of education of the population, the level of medical services, the level of art, the level of development of people's moral standards, spiritual needs and interests. Thus, culture encompasses the achievements of a person in the process of development both in the field of cultural production and spiritual life. It consists of the essence of human knowledge, its work, and is created by previous generations of people. Human culture is growing

and changing, because the current generation can develop further only on the basis of creative use of cultural values of previous generations. Management culture is very important. Humanity has accumulated a great deal of management experience in the course of its development. In market conditions, this experience should serve to improve management efficiency.

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